

Sensors on Sling Load Platform

Evaluation and commissioning of sensors and their integration on the platform

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1. Introduction

The goal of the sensor system is on one side to identify possible collisions with other objects, and on the other side to define the absolute position of the platform, which is the feedback of the position control loop. For this reason, different sensors with different characteristics and costs were evaluated.

2. Laserscanner

Figure 1 RPLidar A2M8

RPLidar A2M8 is a 360° laser scanner with good resolution (1cm), 8 meters scan range and 10 Hz data frequency.

It can therefore be used for position estimation, as well as for collision avoidance, but it detects only objects located along the laser line (2D). The sensors cost around 400 CHF.

2.1 Measurements performance

Item	Unit	Min	Typical	Max	Comments
Distance Range	Meter(m)	0.20	A2M8-R3 and the belowing models	- 8	Based om white objects with 70% reflectivity
			A2M8-R4	- 12	
Angular Range	Degree	-	0-360	-	-
Scan Field Flatness	Degree	-1.5		1.5	
Distance Resolution	mm	-	<0.5 <1% of the distance	-	<1.5 meters All distance range*
Angular Resolution	Degree	0.45	0.9	1.35	10Hz scan rate
Sample Duration	Millisecond(ms)	-	0.125	-	-
Sample Frequency	Hz	2000	8000	8010	
Scan Rate	Hz	5	10	15	The rate is for a round of scan. The typical value is measured when RPLIDAR takes 400 samples per scan

2.2 Communication interface

Item	Unit	Min	Typical	Max	Comments
Band rate	bps	-	115200	-	-
Working mode	-	-	8N1	-	8n1
Output high voltage	Volt (V)	2.9	-	3.5	Logic High
Output low voltage	Volt (V)	-	-	0.4	Logic Low
Input high voltage	Volt (V)	1.6*	-	3.5	Logic High
Input low voltage	Volt (V)	-0.3	-	0.4	Logic Low

2.3 Reference system

Figure 2 Laserscanner reference system

2.4 Software and installations

Public SDK of RPLIDAR products in C++ (open-sourced under GPLv3 license)	Github Code: https://github.com/Slamtec/rplidar_sdk Detailed documentation SDK: https://download.slamtec.com/api/download/rplidar-sdk-manual/1.0?lang=en
Open-Source ROS Node	https://github.com/slamtec/rplidar_ros
Slamtec RoboStudio (Only for sensor evaluation in Windows)	https://www.slamtec.com/robostudio

2.4.1 Installation

- git clone 'repository name'
- cd sdk
- make (Make results are stored under sdk/output/Linux/Release)

2.4.2 Run simple tests

- **sudo ./ultra_simple /dev/ttyUSB0**
- **sudo ./simple_grabber /dev/ttyUSB0**
- /etc/udev/rules.d -> Edit /etc/udev/rules.d
-> Add **KERNEL=="ttyUSB*", MODE=="0666"**, CHECK after Reboot

2.4.3 Integration of SDK in the own Software

Kdevelop settings:

- Terminal -> Type 'Kdevelop' to open a new kdevelop window
- Build configurations: Extra arguments: -
DADDITIONAL_INCLUDE_DIRS=/home/visentin/projects/spark_slingload/software/rplidar_sdk/sdk -
DADDITIONAL_LINK_DIRS=/home/visentin/projects/spark_slingload/software/rplidar_sdk/sdk/output/Linux/Release
- CMakeLists:


```
## Add RPLIDAR SDK
ADD_LIBRARY(rplidar_sdk STATIC IMPORTED)
SET_TARGET_PROPERTIES(rplidar_sdk PROPERTIES
    IMPORTED_LOCATION
    /home/visentin/projects/spark_slingload/software/rplidar_sdk/sdk/output/Linux/Release/librplidar_sdk.a)
## Executables
add_executable(rplidar_test main.cpp)
target_link_libraries(rplidar_test eeros ucl ${CMAKE_DL_LIBS} ${ROS_LIBRARIES} rplidar_sdk)
```

Basis for own code development:

- ROS Wiki: https://github.com/robopeak/rplidar_ros/wiki
- ROS Code: https://github.com/Slamtec/rplidar_ros

3. 3-Axis IMU, SBG

Figure 3 SBG Ellipse-A

Figure 4 SBG Ellipse-A components

SBG Ellipse2-A-G4A3-B2 in Box

- A = AHRS
- G4 = Gyroscope 450°/s
- A3 = Accelerometer 16g
- B2 = Box RS232 + CAN

Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS) have following components: accelerometer, magnetic field, gyroscope. The real reference is the Earth's gravitational and magnetic field. Its static final accuracy depends on the magnetic field measurement accuracy and the gravity measurement accuracy. Gyro determines its dynamic performance.

The more orthogonal of magnetic field and gravitational field, the better the attitude measurement (in the north and south of the magnetic field, the magnetic field is parallel to the gravitational field). In the high latitudes, the local route angle error will increase. At present, the heading solution unit of multi-sensor data fusion adopted in the AHRS is a Kalman filter.

This sensor provides Roll, Pitch, Heading, and Heave data at 200 Hz frequency. It is equipped with 3-axis gyroscopes, accelerometers and magnetometers.

Features

- 0.1° Roll and Pitch over 360°
- 1° Heading (Internal Magnetometers)
- 5 cm Real-time Heave

3.1 Measurement performance

3.1.1 Orientation

	Performance	Remarks
Measurement range	360° in all axes, no mounting limitation	
Roll / Pitch accuracy	< 0.1°	Low dynamic conditions - No long term accelerations
Yaw Accuracy	0.8°	Clean magnetic environment - Magnetic calibration performed

3.1.2 Accelerometers

	A2	A3	A4	Remarks
Full scale (g)	8	16	40	
Scale factor stability (ppm)	1000	1000	1000	After one year accelerated aging
Non-Linearity (ppm of FS)	6300	1500	1500	Best Fit Straight Line
One year bias stability (mg)	2	5	5	After one year accelerated aging
Velocity Random Walk ($\mu\text{g}/\sqrt{\text{hz}}$)	12	57	57	
In run bias instability (μg)	3	14	14	Allan variance - @ 25°C
Vibration Rectification Error ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}^2$)	200	50	50	Tested up to 3g RMS for A2 and 10g RMS for A3/A4
Bandwidth (Hz)	390	390	390	Internal low pass filters attenuation < 3 dB
Sampling rate (kHz)	4	4	4	Advanced anti-aliasing FIR filter
Orthogonality (°)	0.05	0.05	0.05	

3.1.3 Gyroscopes

This gyroscope has good performance in vibrating environments.

- Sampled at 10 kHz
- FIR Filter and coning integral computations

	G4	G5	Remarks
Full scale (°/s)	450	1000	
Scale factor stability (ppm)	500	500	After one year accelerated aging
Non-Linearity (ppm of FS)	50	50	
One year bias stability (°/s)	0.2	0.4	After one year accelerated aging
Angular Random Walk (°/√hr)	0.15	0.18	Allan variance - @ 25°C
In run bias instability (°/hr)	7	8	Allan variance - @ 25°C
Vibration Rectification Error (°/h/g ²)	< 1	< 1	Tested up to 10g RMS
Bandwidth (Hz)	133	133	Internal Gyro bandwidth
Sampling rate (kHz)	10	10	Advanced anti-aliasing FIR filter
Orthogonality (°)	0.05	0.05	

3.1.4 Magnetometer

- Anisotropic magnets have very high sensitivity compared to coil-based technologies
- Magnetometer use requires a specific in place calibration in order to compensate surrounding ferromagnetic materials and magnets. (see Ellipse Hard and Soft Iron Calibration Manual)
 Magnetometer sampling design makes it impossible to reject signal frequencies above 75Hz. User should ensure that high frequency noise is not disturbing magnetometers at the sensor's location.

	Specifications	Remarks
Full scale (Gauss)	50	
Scale factor stability (%)	0,5	
Noise (mGauss)	3	Over 1 to 25 Hz band
Bias stability (m Gauss)	1	
Bandwidth (Hz)	22	-3dB attenuation
Resolution (mGauss)	1.5	
Sampling rate (Hz)	100	
Orthogonality (°)	0.1	After user magnetic calibration

3.2 Communication interface

The Ellipse Serial interfaces support the standard baudrates, up to 921 600 bps. Although it is documented that the max guaranteed baudrate for Linux is 115200, we used the highest, i.e. 921 600 bps.

The Ellipse automatically limits the serial signals slew-rate to minimize EMI and reduce communication error when the baud rate is below 230 400 bps.

In the present application, serial interface is used.

Figure 5 SBG Ellipse-A communication interfaces

3.3 Reference system

3.4 Software ad installations

Available on USB Stick. Is installed under: <C:\Program Files\SBG Systems\Inertial SDK\Software Development\sbgECom> -> Examples -> EllipseMinimal

3.4.1 Windows SDK

Installation

USB Stick -> SDK.exe

License Key: E8ZMU-ASAY2-3TKEV-2UWMX-4S9CS -> sbgCenter Application

Figure 6 Device connection

Figure 7 Available plots

3.4.2 Input / Output Settings

Figure 8 Input / Output settings

Selected Baud Rate = 912600

3.4.3 USB latency time

The latency timer is a form of time-out mechanism for the read buffer of FTDI devices. When a FT_Read instruction is sent to the device, data will not be sent back to the host PC until the requested number of bytes has been read. If the requested number of bytes never comes, the device would not send data back.

The latency timer counts from the last time data was sent back to the PC. If the latency timer expires, the device will send what data it has available to the PC regardless of how many bytes it is waiting on. The latency timer will then reset and begin counting again.

Set Latency Timer to 1 ms, to be able to get sensor messages fast:

- `sudo apt install setserial`
- `setserial dev/ttyUSB0 low_latency`

3.4.4 Important remarks

This model of accelerometer only allows getting data at a frequency rate of 200 Hz. Frequencies of 1 kHz for row data is not possible to reach, we would have needed another model, with an additional interface and cable.

For this reason, the sensor will be used to measure directly an orientation (roll, pitch, yaw) at a rate of 200 Hz. No raw data will be used from the sensor.

4. 1-Axis Accelerometers, Colibrys

Figure 9 Colibrys accelerometer

As an alternative to the SGB sensor, a very precise 1-axis accelerometer was evaluated.

The idea is to place three of these sensors on the platform and read sensors data over analog input, at a higher frequency, around 1000 Hz.

A dedicated documentation for commissioning and analysis of this sensor was developed.

5. Realsense Tracking

Figure 10 Realsense tracking camera

The Intel® RealSense™ Tracking Camera T265 is a stand-alone simultaneous localization and mapping device. It includes two fisheye lens sensors, an IMU and an Intel® Movidius™ Myriad™ 2 VPU. All of the V-SLAM algorithms run directly on the VPU, allowing for very low latency and extremely efficient power consumption. This self-contained tracking system is designed for simple integration. There's no need to re-design your board, simply plug in the provided USB cable and start streaming pose data straight away. The T265 also features an easy mounting solution, with standardized mounting sockets on the rear of the camera.

On image xx it is possible to see all components of the tracking camera.

Figure 11 Realsense Tracking components

5.1 Measurement performance

5.1.1 Inertial measurement

Parameter	Properties
Degrees of Freedom	6
Acceleration Range	$\pm 4g$
Accelerometer Sample Rate	62.5Hz
Gyroscope Range	± 2000 Deg/s
Gyroscope Sample Rate	200Hz

5.1.2 Fisheye image

Parameter	Camera Sensor Properties
Active Pixels	848 X 800
Sensor Aspect Ratio	1.06
Format	8bit, 10-bit RAW
Filter Type	IR Cut Filter
Focus	Fixed
Shutter Type	Global Shutter
Signal Interface	MIPI CSI-2, 2 X Lanes

5.2 Communication interface

5.3 Reference System

Notes:

1. Positive X direction is towards right imager (same for world coordinates)
2. Positive Y direction is upwards toward the top of the device (same for world coordinates)
3. Positive Z direction is inwards toward the back of the device (same for world coordinates)

Figure 12 Realsense tracking - reference system

Figure 13 Realsense tracking - reference system of each component

5.4 Software and installations

Getting started:

<https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-and-tracking-combined-get-started/>
<https://dev.intelrealsense.com/docs/depth-and-tracking-cameras-alignment>

3D Print support: https://github.com/IntelRealSense/realsense-ros/blob/occupancy-mapping/realsense2_camera/meshes/mount_t265_d435.stl

- Corresponding calibration: https://github.com/IntelRealSense/realsense-ros/blob/occupancy-mapping/realsense2_camera/urdf/mount_t265_d435.urdf.xacro

Stereo depth Camera:

- The known information is the **baseline between the two camera lenses**.
- By comparing the image each camera lens sees, and looking at individual points of interest, the depth distance of each pixel in the space (and therefore the distance of each object) can be known essentially by drawing a triangle between the point in space and the two cameras and using trigonometry to infer the distance.

Tracking Camera:

- Understanding the position and movement of the tracking camera.
- The T265 doesn't track external objects, its job is to **track itself with a high degree of accuracy**.
- It does that by using its own set of known information. It has two cameras, which have their own known baseline. It also contains an inertial measurement unit (or IMU), which is a combination of gyroscopes and accelerometers similar to that contained in most modern cellphones.
- The cameras search for visually distinct features in the environment, compare them between the two cameras and then combine that information with the motion of the device from the IMU to enable highly accurate and low latency position data.

Only Tracking camera:

- A robot equipped with the T265 tracking camera can integrate wheel odometry data for a very accurate understanding of its position within the environment
- Would need to pre-map the space around to understand presence of obstacles
- Data can be used to plot a path towards the desired object of interest

Only depth camera:

- Data can be used to avoid obstacles in real-time
- Can also detect downward slopes

Windows installation:

- <https://www.intelrealsense.com/sdk-2/>
- <https://dev.intelrealsense.com/docs/installing-intel-realsense-sdk-20-for-windows>

Run SW Examples on Windows / Visual Studio:

- <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/support/articles/000030463/emerging-technologies/intel-realsense-technology.html>

Realsense Viewer

Camera D435

Figure 14 Realsense tracking - Window / Trees

Figure 15 Realsense tracking - Wall outdoor

Tracking T265

Figure 16 Realsense tracking – Overview (Windows)

Figure 17 Realsense tracking + D435 – Overview (Windows)

5.5 Tracking Accuracy

Intel:

<https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/support/articles/000032899/emerging-technologies/intel-realsense-technology.html>

-> 1 Percent of travelled distance

"For example, if the total distance traveled is 10 meters, then it is expected that the robot can be off by 1 percent of 10 meters, which is .1m, from the starting point"

Other source: Test with ROS

<https://jaspereb.github.io/TestingRealsenseT265/>

Test 1: cartesian trajectory, moving along the x axis then the z axis (in an L shape), 47.5s

Test 2: random trajectory, with complicated orientation changes, 28.5 s

Test 3: random trajectory with camera covered -> test quality of the IMU

Remarks of the author

Performance was not quite as good as I expected, showing errors of up to 10cm for periods of high acceleration. However, the VSLAM loop closure does work and the tracking is good for periods of constant velocity, so long term drift should not be a problem in small environments.

6. Baumer Laser distance sensors

Baumer sensors ensure precise distance, spacing and position measurements. They have best-in-class measurement performance for reliable processes and greater system availability, intuitive operating concept for the efficient optimization of the sensor ensures shorter application development and on-the-fly parameterization.

Those sensors were selected for their high precision (2 μm) and high frequency rate (1000 Hz). In this way it is possible to test the stiffness of the control loop, since the sensors bandwidth is not influencing it.

Price range is about 1400 CHF for each sensor. Three sensors were mounted on the platform, two one one side and one on another side. In this way it is possible to measure the displacement along two directions (x, y) and the rotation around the z axis.

6.1 Measuring range and positioning

Figure 18 Baumer laser sensors details

The mounting of the platform led to a possible issue, which is represented in Figure 19. Sensors mounted near to each other in this configuration could indeed lead to interferences. After proof of the final setup, we could confirm that in our case the interferences are outside the measuring field.

Figure 19 Sensors cross-disturbances

Figure 20 Check of possible sensors cross-disturbances

6.2 Communication interface

6.2.1 IP Adresses

PC	192.168.0.251
Sensor 1	192.168.0.252
Sensor 2	192.168.0.253
Sensor 3	192.168.0.254

6.2.2 Device configuration over web interface

Sensor Info i

Sensor Type: **OM70-P0250.HH0240.EK**

Serial Number: **700005019409**

P-Code: **L445**

Network i

Static IP Address

IP Address:

Subnet Mask:

Standard Gateway:

DHCP OFF

Process Interface i

Profinet ON

Modbus TCP ON

OPC UA ON

UDP Streaming OFF

IP Address:

Port:

6.2.3 Modbus

Link Documentation: <https://libmodbus.org/documentation/>

6.4.2.1 Overview of index commands Input Register Function 04

The following table shows an overview of commands. In the following chapters the respective commands are explained:

Address	Size [Byte]	Command	Description
0	33	Vendor Information	Vendor name
40	45	Device Information	Information for device
90	5	Frontend Version	Informationen for frontend
100	6	Ethernet Configuration	Reading IP/ Subnet/ Gateway address
120	6	MAC Address	Reading MAC address
150	6	Meas Range Limits	Measuring Range Limits
200	17	All Measurements	Measuring values and additional information
250	14	Teachable Range	Configuration of Switching Output
300	2	Hold Time Limits	Limiting Hold Time
400	1	Unsaved Configuration	Display status unsaved configuration
401	1	Active Setting Number	Show active Parameter Setup number
410	28	Get Setting 1	Show Parameter Setup 1
450	28	Get Setting 2	Show Parameter Setup 2
490	28	Get Setting 3	Show Parameter Setup 3
600	112	Get Block Mode Memory 0	Reading stored measured values block 0
712	112	Get Block Mode Memory 1	Reading stored measured values block 1
824	112	Get Block Mode Memory 2	Reading stored measured values block 2
936	112	Get Block Mode Memory 3	Reading stored measured values block 3
1048	112	Get Block Mode Memory 4	Reading stored measured values block 4
1160	112	Get Block Mode Memory 5	Reading stored measured values block 5
1272	112	Get Block Mode Memory 6	Reading stored measured values block 6
1384	112	Get Block Mode Memory 7	Reading stored measured values block 7
1496	112	Get Block Mode Memory 8	Reading stored measured values block 8
1608	112	Get Block Mode Memory 9	Reading stored measured values block 9
1720	112	Get Block Mode Memory 10	Reading stored measured values block 10
1832	112	Get Block Mode Memory 11	Reading stored measured values block 11
1944	112	Get Block Mode Memory 12	Reading stored measured values block 12
2056	112	Get Block Mode Memory 13	Reading stored measured values block 13
2168	112	Get Block Mode Memory 14	Reading stored measured values block 14

6.4.2.8 Address 200 - All Measurements

Address	Access	Length	Datatype	Description
200	Read	1	uint16_t	General Status Bit 0: State Configurationmode 0 = Inactive 1 = Active Bit 1: NTP-Timeserver Synchronisation 0 = Inactive 1 = Active Bit 2: State Warmup 0 = Inactive 1 = Active
201	Read	1	uint16_t	Quality of Measuring signal 0 = ok 1 = low signal 2 = no signal
202	Read	1	uint16_t	Bit 0: State Switching Output 0 = Active 1 = Inactive Bit 1: State Alarm Output 0 = Active 1 = Inactive
203 - 204	Read	2	float32_t	Distance [mm]
205 - 206	Read	2	float32_t	Measurement Rate [Hz]
207 - 208	Read	2	float32_t	Exposure Reserve
209 - 210	Read	2	uint32_t	Response Delay seconds [s: μ s]
211 - 212	Read	2	uint32_t	Response delay microseconds [s: μ s]
213 - 214	Read	2	uint32_t	Time stamp seconds [s: μ s]
215 - 216	Read	2	uint32_t	Time stamp microseconds [s: μ s]

6.2.4 Final settings data acquisition rate

Alarm ■ Switching Output ■

|| Pause

> Active Parameters ⓘ

1 Data Acquisition ^

Trigger Mode ⓘ

Free Running

Trigger Interval μ s

Single Shot

2 Measuring Range ▾

3 Output & Filter ▾

4 Save Parameters ▾

If the sensor is connected to the laptop over ethernet, it is possible to type the ip address of the sensor on the web browser and enter the parametrization window.

Following parameters are used:
 Data acquisition: Trigger interval 550 μ s
 Measuring range: full measuring range
 Other parameters left to default values.

7. Pixy Camera

Figure 21 PixyCam2

The Pixy2 can learn to detect objects and has new algorithms that detect and track lines for use with line-following robots. With color-based filtering algorithms it is possible to identify markers on the floor and use then to get absolute position and orientation,

The board is provided with:

- Aptina MT9M114 1296×976 resolution image sensor
- Dual core NXP LPC4330 204 MHz processor

Figure 22 Markers on the floor

An additional evaluated option is this pixy camera. The frame rate of 60 fps was interesting, since lower bandwidth showed a massive reduction of system's control bandwidth. Color-based features recognition can be set with an available tool and the position of the feature in the picture is returned in pixels. This system led to a positioning precision under a centimeter.

Figure 23 PixyCam on sensor platform

Figure 24 PixyCam on sensor platform